

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF CYANOMACLURIN AND RELATED SUBSTANCES. PART II*

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6-Methoxycoumaranone has been condensed with salicylaldehyde, β -resoreylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-4:6-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde in presence of piperidine to give the corresponding arylidene-coumaranones in good yields. Excepting 6-methoxy-2-(2:4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-coumaranone, all these arylidene-coumaranones are reduced to the corresponding aryl derivatives. The aryl-coumaranones have been cyclised by means of phosphorus pentoxide to the corresponding chromene derivatives.

Previous attempts at the synthesis of cyanomaclurin, notably by Bhalla and Ray (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 288) and Fonseca (*ibid.*, 1947, 1683), aimed at synthesising a structure (I) as assigned by Perkin (*ibid.*, 1905, 87, 714) to cyanomaclurin. Since, however, the semi-acetal formula (II) for cyanomaclurin, as proposed by Appel and Robinson (*ibid.*, 1935, 752), seemed to be more plausible on available chemical and physical evidences, attempts have now been made to synthesise a substance corresponding to the semi-acetal structure.

(I)

(II)

The initial step in one of the two schemes envisaged for this purpose was the preparation of the methiodide of a Mannich base from phloroglucinol or its methyl ether and its subsequent condensation with 6-methoxycoumaranone (cf. Robinson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53; 1941, 589; Wilds and Shunk, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 469). The resulting tetracyclic condensation product (III), a benzofuranochromene derivative, on epoxidation with a per-acid could give an epoxide (IV), which on subsequent catalytic hydrogenation could furnish either (V) and/ or (VI). Thus:

(III)

(IV)

*Part I—Bhalla and Ray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 288.

However, the Mannich reaction with phloroglucinol or its methyl ether has been reported by De'Combe (*Compt. rend.*, 1933, 197, 258) to give resinous products. This observation has been confirmed by the present authors. Therefore, attempts were made to prepare a Mannich base from 6-methoxycoumaranone which in the form of its methiodide was expected to condense with phloroglucinol to give (III). Despite numerous attempts 6-methoxycoumaranone failed to provide a definite compound in the Mannich reaction with dimethylamine and formaldehyde. This we attribute to its reacting in two tautomeric forms.

In the alternative route, which was then examined, the initial step consisted in the condensation of an appropriate *ortho*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with 6-methoxycoumaranone. The resulting condensation product (VII), an arylidene-coumaranone, could then be reduced catalytically and the reduction product, (VIII), cyclised according to standard methods, thus giving rise to a benzofuranochromene derivative (III), as contemplated in the earlier scheme.

In order to explore the method, experiments were first carried out with salicylaldehyde. It was condensed with 6-methoxycoumaranone in presence of piperidine to give 6-methoxy-2-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)-coumaranone in excellent yield (cf. Auwers and Pohl, *Annalen*, 1914, 405, 243; Shriner and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 1415).

6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)-coumaranone on catalytic hydrogenation with palladium gave 6-methoxy-2-(2-hydroxybenzyl)-coumaranone. The reduction product was cyclised by refluxing its solution in dry benzene with phosphorus pentoxide, when 2:3-(3':2':6'-methoxybenzofurano)-chromene was obtained in good yield. When this chromene was subjected to epoxidation with monopero-phthalic acid in ether solution at 0°, only phthalic acid and a red coloured pasty product were obtained. The use of an inert atmosphere or application of a modified method (Chakravarty and Levine, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2319) of epoxidation with perbenzoic acid gave similar results. With 30% hydrogen peroxide (Rohrman, Jones and Shonle, *ibid.*, 1944, 66, 1854), the unchanged chromene was the only product isolated.

Similarly, β -resorcyaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-4:6-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde smoothly condensed with 6-methoxycoumaranone in presence of piperidine to give respectively 6-methoxy-2-(2:4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-, 6-methoxy-2-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzylidene)-, 6-methoxy-2-(2-hydroxy-4:6-dimethoxybenzylidene)- and 6-methoxy-2-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)-coumaranones in good yields. Excepting 6-methoxy-2-(2:4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-coumaranone, all other arylidene-coumaranones could be reduced to the corresponding aryl-coumaranones. The reduction products, when cyclised, as described above, gave rise to the corresponding chromene derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)-coumaranone (VII: $R_1 = R_2 = H$).—6-Methoxycoumaranone (1 g.) and salicylaldehyde (0.8 g.) were dissolved in hot alcohol (10 c.c.) and then piperidine (1 c.c.) was added dropwise. The solution which became deep red in colour was left at room temperature overnight. It was then filtered from the separated yellow crystalline material which was recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 258-59° (decomp.), yield 1.6 g. (95%). (Found: C, 71.6; H, 4.4. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5%). The acetyl derivative was crystallised from rectified spirit or ethyl acetate in pale yellow needles, m.p. 163-65°. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 69.7; H, 4.5%).

6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxybenzyl)-coumaranone (VIII: $R_1 = R_2 = H$).—6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)-coumaranone (1 g.) was dissolved in sufficient quantity of hot alcohol (ca. 300 c.c.) and the solution transferred to a hydrogenation bottle. Palladium chloride solution (1 c.c. of 1%) and a little purified charcoal were then added and the reduction carried out in a Parr hydrogenation apparatus. Within about one hour the solution became colorless. It was filtered and on removal of the solvent a colorless crystalline compound was obtained which was recrystallised from methyl alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 145°, yield 0.6 g. (60%). (Found: C, 71.0; H, 5.5. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 71.1; H, 5.2%).

2:3-(3':2':6'-Methoxybenzofurano)-chromene (III: $R_1 = R_2 = H$).—6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxybenzyl)-coumaranone (1 g.) was dissolved in hot dry benzene and P_2O_5 (ca. 2 g.) was added to the solution, which was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours, and then decanted off. On removal of benzene a colorless crystalline compound was obtained which was recrystallised from methyl alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 108°, yield 0.5 g. (45-50%). (Found: C, 76.3; H, 5.1. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.8%).

6-Methoxy-2-(2:4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-coumaranone (VII: $R_1 = OH$; $R_2 = H$).—6-Methoxycoumaranone (1 g.) and β -resorcyaldehyde (1.38 g.) were dissolved in hot alcohol (10 c.c.) and to the hot solution piperidine (1 c.c.) was added dropwise. After 24 hours the crystalline solid, which had separated, was collected and recrystallised from alcohol or acetic acid, m.p. 244-46° (decomp.), yield 1.3 g. (45%). (Found: C, 67.4; H, 4.5. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 67.6; H, 4.23%). The acetyl derivative was

crystallised from alcohol in colorless tiny needles, m.p. 159-61°. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 4.4. $C_{20}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 65.2; H, 4.3%).

6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzylidene)-coumaranone (VII: $R_1 = OMe$; $R_2 = H$):—6-Methoxycoumaranone (1.64 g., 0.01 M) and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde (1.52 g., 0.01 M) were condensed as before. The product, an orange-coloured crystalline solid, was recrystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 223-25° (decomp.), yield 2.8 g. (95%). (Found: C, 68.9; H, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.5; H, 4.7%). The acetyl derivative was crystallised from alcohol in tiny needles, m.p. 156-57° (Found: C, 66.8; H, 4.2. $C_{19}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 67.1; H, 4.7%).

6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzyl)-coumaranone (VIII; $R_1 = OMe$; $R_2 = H$):—The reduction of 6-methoxy-2-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)-coumaranone was carried out by shaking its solution in alcohol (1 g. in about 250 c.c.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of palladium on charcoal, as described before. The resulting colorless solution was filtered and the filtrate diluted considerably with water when a crystalline material separated out. It was recrystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 113-15°, yield 0.7-0.8 g. (65-70%). (Found: C, 64.0; H, 5.5. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5 \cdot H_2O$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.7%).

7-Methoxy-2:3-(3':2':6'-methoxybenzofurano)-chromene (III: $R_1 = OMe$; $R_2 = H$):—The preceding coumaranone (1 g.) was dissolved in hot dry benzene and P_2O_5 (ca. 2 g.) was added to the solution which was then refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours, and then decanted off. On removal of benzene a crystalline solid was obtained which was recrystallised from methyl alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 139-40°, yield 0.5 g. (55%). (Found: C, 72.4; H, 5.4. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 72.4; H, 5.0%).

6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxy-4:6-dimethoxybenzylidene)-coumaranone (VII: $R_1 = R_2 = OMe$):—6-Methoxycoumaranone (1.64 g., 0.01 M) and 2-hydroxy-4:6-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (1.82 g., 0.01 M) were condensed as before and the orange-coloured crystalline solid so obtained was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 173-74°, yield 2.3 g. (70%). (Found: C, 65.9; H, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 65.9; H, 4.9%). The acetyl derivative was crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 135-37°. (Found: C, 64.4; H, 4.9. $C_{20}H_{20}O_7$ requires C, 64.5; H, 5.1%).

6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxy-4:6-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumaranone (VIII: $R_1 = R_2 = OMe$):—The reduction of the preceding coumaranone (1 g.), when carried out as described before, afforded a colorless crystalline solid which was recrystallised from aqueous methyl alcohol, m.p. 170-72°, yield 0.7 g. (70%). (Found: C, 64.9; H, 5.5. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 64.5; H, 5.5%).

5:7-Dimethoxy-2:3-(3':2':6'-methoxybenzofurano)-chromene (III: $R_1 = R_2 = OMe$):—To the hot solution of the above coumaranone (1 g.) in dry benzene P_2O_5 (ca. 2 g.) was added and after refluxing for 2 hours, the solution was decanted off. On removal of benzene a solid was obtained which was crystallised from aqueous methyl alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 160-62°, yield 0.6 g. (70%). (Found: C, 69.5; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 69.2; H, 5.1%).

6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxynaphthylidene)-coumaranone.—6-Methoxycoumaranone (3.3 g., 0.02 M) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (3.44 g., 0.02 M) were condensed as before. The product, an orange-coloured solid, was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 176-78°, yield 5.5 g. (85-90%). (Found: C, 75.4; H, 4.4. $C_{20}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 4.4%). The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 147-49°. (Found: C, 73.3; H, 4.6. $C_{22}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.3; H, 4.4%).

6-Methoxy-2-(2-hydroxynaphthyl)-coumaranone.—The reduction of the preceding coumaranone (1 g.), when carried out as described before, gave a colorless crystalline solid which was recrystallised from aqueous methyl alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 167-68° (decomp.), yield 0.8 g., (80%). (Found: C, 74.7; H, 5.2. $C_{20}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0%).

2:3-(2':3':6'-Methoxybenzofurano)-1-benzo(f)-chromene.—6-Methoxy-2-(hydroxynaphthyl)-coumaranone (1 g.) was cyclised as before. The product, a colorless crystalline solid, was recrystallised from aqueous methyl alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 182-83°, yield 0.7 g. (70%). (Found: C, 79.2; H, 4.7. $C_{20}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 79.5; H, 4.6%).

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